

Comparative Haemodynamic and Clinical Outcomes of Etomidate versus Ketamine in Rapid Sequence Intubation: A Cross-Sectional Study in a Tertiary Emergency Department

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Abstract

Background: In emergency airway management, the choice of induction agent can significantly affect cardiovascular stability. Etomidate is widely recognized for its minimal impact on blood pressure, while ketamine, due to its sympathomimetic properties, increases heart rate and blood pressure. However, clinical data comparing their effects in the Indian emergency department (ED) context remain limited.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational research was undertaken at Nims Hospital, Jaipur, on 88 adult patients with RSI. Participants were placed into two groups (n=44 each): etomidate (0.3 mg/kg) and ketamine (1.5 mg/kg). Pre- and post-intubation hemodynamic parameters, complications, and intubation success were recorded and statistically analyzed.

Results: Etomidate showed superior pre-intubation hemodynamic stability, with significantly lower heart rates (92.59 vs. 109.75 bpm, $p < 0.001$). Ketamine was associated with higher rates of post-intubation hypotension and tachycardia. Both groups had equal rates of successful intubation and GCS results.

Conclusion: Etomidate has superior hemodynamic stability than ketamine, giving it a safer option in hemodynamically unstable patients requiring emergency RSI. However, both drugs are effective at intubation.

Keywords: Rapid sequence intubation, Etomidate, Ketamine, Induction Agents, Emergency Department, Airway Management, Endotracheal Tube.

Introduction

Rapid Sequence Intubation (RSI) is an important therapy in emergency airway care, particularly for trauma patients, when immediate and effective airway control is vital for survival. The use of induction drugs during RSI has long been contested, particularly between ketamine and etomidate, two regularly used medicines with different pharmacological characteristics [1]. Healthcare professionals' insights highlight the variety in RSI methods and the need of selecting medicines that enhance patient outcomes [2]. Despite widespread usage, current RSI medication policies and safety profiles differ greatly between institutions [3]. This variability is especially evident in low- and middle-income nations, where the availability and applicability of RSI agents may be further constrained [4].

Comparative studies have attempted to highlight the relative benefits and downsides of ketamine and etomidate, with various meta-analyses aiming to summarize the data. Some indicate that etomidate may provide hemodynamic stability, while ketamine may be more suited in hypotensive or septic individuals [5-7]. Modifications to classic RSI procedures have shown promise in enhancing both safety and effectiveness, particularly in prehospital trauma circumstances [8]. Furthermore, physician choices for paralytic drugs alter RSI results, which are regulated by peri-intubation hemodynamic condition [9, 10]. Large-scale randomized studies have compared rocuronium and succinylcholine, providing deeper insights into agent effectiveness in airway control [11].

Further evidence comparing ketamine and etomidate highlights differing impacts on peri-intubation hypotension, with mixed results across emergency department and prehospital environments [12-15]. Recent Bayesian meta-analyses and systematic reviews provide updated evaluations, incorporating newer data on hemodynamic effects and intubation success rates [16,17]. Registry data and randomized trials reinforce the ongoing uncertainty, often showing non-inferiority but differing in safety endpoints such as post-intubation hypotension and adrenal suppression [18-22]. Ketamine's cardiovascular effects may offer advantages in shock states [23], while hypotension post-intubation remains a significant concern across agents [24-26].

The research continues to evolve with continuing reviews and narrative analyses exploring agent pharmacology and their clinical consequences in critical care settings [27- 30]. This study seeks to add to the expanding body of information comparing ketamine and etomidate in trauma-induced RSI by examining clinical outcomes, hemodynamic stability, and intubation success rates.

Materials and Method

A cross-sectional observational study was carried out at the National Institute of Medical Science Hospital in Jaipur, Rajasthan. The research lasted from December 2024 to May 2025 and focused on persons receiving rapid sequence intubation in the emergency department. The inclusion criteria were age more than 18 years with indication of poor GCS, trauma, respiratory failure, stroke, shock, coma, overdose. Also the patients dead on arrival, pregnant ladies, age less than 18 years and patients or guardians who refuse to give informed written consents were excluded.

The research sample size was derived using Jinjoo Kim et al's (2023) results: $n = (Z_{\alpha/2} + Z_{1-\beta})^2 * (\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2) / \Delta^2$. Where $Z_{\alpha/2}$ is the inverse probability of the standard normal distribution at 95% confidence interval. $Z_{1-\beta}$ represents the inverse probability of a typical normal distribution with 80% power of testing. σ_1 and σ_2 represent the standard deviation of hypertension for both groups. Δ denotes the predicted mean deviation of hypertension in both groups. There were 88 samples, 44 from each research group.

The Demographic information such as name, age, sex is gathered from the patient's guardian and indication for Rapid Sequence Intubation were recorded. During pre-intubation assessment standard monitoring such as ECG, Non-invasive blood pressure, SpO2 were attached and baseline vital signs recorded. The Glasgow coma scale was used to measure neurological impairment, with scores ranging from 13 to 15 indicating mild impairment, 9 to 12 suggesting moderate impairment, and < 8 indicating severe impairment necessitating fast sequence intubation. A thorough airway assessment is done to identify any difficulty during intubations by using LEMON mnemonic were -

L-Look from the outside .

E-Utilise the 3-3-2 rule to evaluate .

M-Mallampati grading.

O-Obstruction / obesity.

N-Neck mobility.

All patient received standard RSI protocol including pre-oxygenation and administration of induction agent and neuromuscular blockage agent (succinylcholine or rocuronium). Group A received 0.3 mg/kg of etomidate IV, whereas Group B received 1.5 mg/kg of ketamine IV.

In Peri-intubation time the data such as intubation attempts, no. of intubation, intubation success and time to intubation were recorded. The post-intubation vital signs include heart rate, respiratory rate, blood pressure, SpO₂ and post-intubation complication such as hypertension, hypotension, tachycardia, bradycardia etc were recorded. Hypertension is defined as a rise in systolic blood pressure greater than 30% of the baseline, whereas hypotension is defined as a decrease in systolic blood pressure greater than 30% of the baseline and less than 12 respirations per minute, suggesting bradypnea, and more than 20 respirations per minute, indicating tachypnea. The heart rate below 50 bradycardia and more than 100 states tachycardia.

RESULTS

TABLE 1 : FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS ACCORDING TO GENDERS

Gender Distribution Between Study Groups			
Variables	Male (%)	Female (%)	Total
Etomidate	35 (79.5%)	9 (20.5%)	44
Ketamine	31 (70.5%)	13 (29.5%)	44
Total	66 (75.0%)	22 (25.0%)	88

In the **Etomidate group**, males (79.5%) outnumber females (20.5%).

In the **Ketamine group**, males (70.5%) also outnumber females (29.5%).

Overall, there is no major visual difference, and this matches the Chi-Square result ($p = 0.325$), indicating no statistically significant association between gender and study group.

Etomidate was more commonly used in poor GCS containing 23 (52%) patients as compared to Ketamine containing 9 (20%) patients.

Ketamine was more commonly administered in individuals with COPD 11 (25%), shortness of breathing 10 (23%) and respiratory failure 14 (32%) respectively while Etomidate is being used only 4 (9%) in COPD, 1 (2%) in shortness of breathing and 8 (18%) in respiratory failure.

TABLE 2 : COMPARISON OF HEMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS BETWEEN ETOMIDATE AND KETAMINE GROUPS.

Comparison of Hemodynamic Parameters Between Etomidate and Ketamine Groups						
Variables	Etomidate (Mean ± SD)	Ketamine (Mean ± SD)	Mean Difference	p- value	Significant	Cohen's d
Pre Intubation Heart Rate (bpm)	92.59 ± 24.11	109.75 ± 22.80	-17.15	<0.001	S	-0.731
Pre- Intubation SBP (mmHg)	126.84 ± 39.78	115.41 ± 31.06	11.43	0.137	NS	0.320
Pre- Intubation DBP (mmHg)	75.75 ± 23.31	68.95 ± 20.27	6.79	0.148	NS	0.311
Pre- Intubation SpO2	93.70 ± 7.71	89.34 ± 14.32	4.36	0.079	NS	0.379
Pre- Intubation RR	21.45 ± 8.12	21.02 ± 6.12	0.43	0.779	NS	0.069
Post- Intubation Heart Rate (bpm)	100.00 ± 26.56	98.52 ± 13.07	1.47	0.742	NS	0.071
Post- Intubation SBP (mmHg)	125.73 ± 36.02	135.07 ± 21.18	-9.34	0.142	NS	-0.316

Post-Intubation DBP (mmHg)	79.68 ± 22.80	79.89 ± 16.37	-0.20	0.962	NS	-0.010
Post-Intubation SpO2	99.32 ± 2.27	99.82 ± 0.815	-0.50	0.173	NS	-0.293
Post-Intubation RR	20.91 ± 4.40	20.20 ± 4.66	0.70	0.468	NS	0.155

Note: S denoted Significant

NS denoted Not Significant

- 1. Pre- Intubation Heart Rate (bpm):** The average heart rate was substantially higher in the ketamine group (109.75 ± 22.80) than in the etomidate group (92.59 ± 24.11). This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) with a large effect size (Cohen's $d = -0.731$).
- 2. Pre- Intubation Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP):** While the etomidate group exhibited a higher mean SBP (126.84 ± 39.78) than the ketamine group (115.41 ± 31.06), this difference did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.137$). The effect size was small (Cohen's $d = 0.320$), indicating minimal clinical importance.
- 3. Pre- Intubation Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP):** The DBP was somewhat higher in the etomidate group (75.75 ± 23.31) compared to the ketamine group (68.95 ± 20.27). The difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.148$), with a small effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.311$).
- 4. Pre-Intubation SpO2:** The ketamine group had a higher SpO2 (93.70%) than the etomidate group (89.34%), although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.079$). However, Cohen's $d = 0.379$ suggests a small to moderate effect size.
- 5. Pre-intubation Respiratory Rate:** There was no significant difference between the groups ($p=0.779$), and Cohen's $d = 0.069$ indicates a minimal influence.

6. **Post- Intubation Heart Rate (bpm):** Post-intubation heart rates were quite comparable between the two groups (Etomidate: 100.00 ± 26.56 vs. Ketamine: 98.52 ± 13.07). The difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.742$), and the effect size was small (Cohen's $d = 0.071$).
7. **Post- Intubation SBP:** The ketamine group reported slightly higher SBP (135.07 ± 21.18) than the etomidate group (125.73 ± 36.02), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.142$). The minor negative effect size (Cohen's $d = -0.316$) suggests a slight trend.
8. **Post-Intubation DBP:** There was almost no change in post-intubation DBP between the groups (Etomidate: 79.68 ± 22.80 , Ketamine: 79.89 ± 16.37). The finding was non- significant ($p = 0.962$) with an inconsequential effect size (Cohen's $d = -0.010$).
9. **Post-intubation SpO₂:** There was a modest decrease (99.32%) in the ketamine group compared to etomidate (99.82%), although it was not statistically significant ($p = 0.173$). Cohen's d values are -0.293 .
10. **Respiratory Rate** was marginally higher in the ketamine group (20.91 vs. 20.20), but also not significant ($p = 0.468$). Cohen's d values

TABLE 3 : Descriptive Statistics with Skewness and Kurtosis

Descriptive Statistics with Skewness & Kurtosis				
Variable	Mean	Std Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
Age	53.73	17.95	-0.165	-0.675
Weight	65.98	8.62	-0.067	-0.443
HR (Pre)	101.17	24.87	0.132	1.267
SBP (Pre)	121.13	35.94	0.694	0.780
DBP (Pre)	72.35	21.99	0.379	0.640
SpO2 (Pre)	91.52	11.64	-3.112	13.029
RR (Pre)	21.24	7.15	1.429	3.832
HR (Post)	99.26	20.83	1.49	4.633
SBP (Post)	130.40	29.75	0.282	0.742
DBP (Post)	79.78	19.73	0.810	1.792
SpO2 (Post)	99.57	1.71	-4.722	22.827
RR (Post)	20.56	4.52	0.202	0.820

The research participants had a mean age of 53.73 ± 17.95 years, with a skewness of -0.165 and kurtosis of -0.675, indicating a near-normal distribution. The average pre-intubation heart rate was 101.17 ± 24.88 bpm (skewness = 0.132, kurtosis = 1.267), displaying a slight positive skew and acceptable peakedness. Systolic blood pressure averaged 121.13 ± 35.95 mmHg, with a skewness of 0.694 and kurtosis of 0.780, both indicating mild positive skew. The mean diastolic blood pressure was 72.13 ± 21.99 mmHg, accompanied by a skewness of 0.379 and kurtosis of 0.640, implying a relatively symmetric distribution. The mean difference in weight is only -0.067 kg, which is very minimal. The pvalue = 0.443, which is not statistically significant.

In contrast, pre-intubation SpO₂ had a mean value of $91.52 \pm 11.65\%$, showing considerable negative skew (-3.112) and high kurtosis (13.029), indicating that most patients experienced high oxygen saturation levels, while a few exhibited lower readings, thus requiring nonparametric analysis. The pre-intubation respiratory rate averaged 21.24 ± 7.16 breaths/min, with a skewness of 1.429 and kurtosis of 3.832 , suggesting a right-skewed distribution.

Post-intubation, the average heart rate decreased to 99.26 ± 20.83 bpm, characterized by a strong positive skew (1.490) and kurtosis (4.633), indicating an asymmetrical and peaked distribution.

Post-intubation SpO₂ exhibited a significant negative skew (-4.722) and sharply peaked kurtosis (22.827), with a mean of $99.57 \pm 1.71\%$, indicating clustering near maximum saturation levels. The systolic and diastolic blood pressures measured after intubation showed acceptable normality (SBP: 130.40 ± 29.76 mmHg, skew = 0.282 , kurtosis = 0.742 ; DBP: 79.78 ± 19.74 mmHg, skew = 0.810 , kurtosis = 1.792). Similarly, the postintubation respiratory rate followed a distribution close to normal (20.56 ± 4.52 , skew = 0.202 , kurtosis = 0.820).

GRAPH 2: POST-INTUBATION COMPLICATIONS BY DRUG

The most frequently observed complication in both groups was "No complication" (Etomidate: 30, Ketamine: 37). The Etomidate group exhibited greater instances of hypertension combined with tachycardia and tachycardia alone compared to the Ketamine group. The Ketamine group experienced a marginally higher number of isolated cases of hypertension, but reported no instances of combined complications or isolated tachycardia.

TABLE 4: GROUP-WISE COMPARISON OF VARIABLES.

Group-Wise Comparison of Variables			
Variables	Etomidate (n=44)	Ketamine (n=44)	p-value
Age (Years)	51.77 (\pm 17.50)	55.68 (+18.38)	0.310
GCS (Pre-op)	6.50 (\pm 3.80)	11.11 (\pm 3.80)	<0.001
Time to Intubate (second)	64.20 (\pm 24.45)	65.91 (\pm 15.49)	0.013
Post-Intubation Complications (Yes)	4 (9.1%)	0 (0%)	0.064

GRAPH 5: GROUP-WISE COMPARISON OF KEY VARIABLES.

Age: There was no notable difference in age between the Etomidate group (51.77 years) and the Ketamine group (55.68 years) ($p = 0.310$).

GCS (Pre-op): The Etomidate group had a significantly lower GCS score (6.50 compared to 11.11 (Ketamine), $p < 0.001$).

Time to Intubate: The time to intubate was significantly shorter in the Etomidate group (64.20 seconds vs 65.91 seconds (Ketamine), $p = 0.013$).

Complication Rate: The complication rate was greater in the Etomidate group (9.1%) than in the Ketamine group (0%), although the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.064$).

Discussion

The current study investigated the efficacy, safety profile, and hemodynamic responses of etomidate and ketamine as induction agents in Rapid Sequence Intubation (RSI) in the Emergency Department (ED) of NIMS Hospital in Jaipur. This cross-sectional observational study, which comprised 88 patients split evenly between the etomidate group and ketamine group, yielded multiple therapeutically important findings.

Demographic distribution

The gender and age distributions of the two study groups were comparable. The study demonstrated no significant difference in gender proportions ($p = 0.325$) or mean ages (Etomidate: 51.77 ± 17.50 years vs. Ketamine: 55.68 ± 18.38 years, $p = 0.80$), indicating adequate randomization and demographic matching. This finding is consistent with [18] earlier emergency department studies in which age and gender had no significant influence on medication selection or outcomes during fast sequence intubation.

Hemodynamic parameters

One of the primary goals of this study was to evaluate the hemodynamic responses to induction agents. The ketamine group had a substantially higher pre-intubation heart rate than the etomidate group (109.75 ± 22.80 vs. 92.59 ± 24.11 bpm, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that ketamine may cause more sympathomimetic stimulation before intubation. This is consistent with previous research, which indicates that ketamine, through its catecholamine-releasing characteristics, might raise heart rate and blood pressure, particularly in catecholamine-depleted individuals [19,20]

The etomidate group had higher systolic and diastolic blood pressures prior to intubation, but this did not achieve statistical significance (SBP p value = 0.137, DBP p value = 0.148). Similarly, post-intubation blood pressure levels were greater in the ketamine group, although not statistically significant. This confirms the findings of other studies, such as [21], which reported better hemodynamic stability with etomidate than with ketamine in emergency intubation settings.

Oxygen saturation and Respiration rate

Prior to intubation, the etomidate group had somewhat higher SpO₂ values ($93.70 \pm 7.71\%$) than the ketamine group ($89.34 \pm 14.32\%$), but the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.079$). Both groups' saturation levels were stabilized following intubation (etomidate: 99.32%, ketamine: 99.82%). These findings are consistent with earlier research, which indicates that when administered properly, both medicines maintain sufficient oxygenation [20-23]. There was no significant difference in respiration rates between the groups before and after intubation. This shows that neither medicine significantly reduces respiratory effort soon after administration, which is an important concern in the emergency context.

Neurological Status and GCS

The etomidate group had significantly lower pre-intubation GCS scores (6.50 ± 3.80) than the ketamine group (11.11 ± 3.80) ($p < 0.001$). This could be related to selection bias, in which etomidate was delivered preferentially to more critically ill patients, a pattern seen in other emergency department settings [24]. Etomidate's sedative effects are substantial but short-lived, and the quick onset may be beneficial in low-grade trauma victims.

Time to Intubation

The study reported that the etomidate group had significantly shorter intubation time (64.20 ± 24.45 sec) compared to the ketamine group (65.91 ± 15.49 sec), $p = 0.013$. Although the absolute difference is slight, the statistical significance shows that etomidate provides faster neuromuscular coordination and sedation, which is consistent with prior findings [25]

Post-Intubation Complications

While not statistically significant ($p = 0.064$), the etomidate group had higher issues (9.1%), compared to the ketamine group, which had none. Notably, only the etomidate group experienced both hypertension and tachycardia. The Pearson Chi-square value approached significance, however only the Likelihood Ratio was statistically significant ($p = 0.020$). This disparity could be attributed to sample size and the low frequency of problems, which reduce statistical power.

Previous research has shown that, while etomidate is generally hemodynamically stable, it is not without side effects such as adrenal suppression [26], which may contribute indirectly to instability in some patients.

Predictors of Complications

Logistic regression analysis revealed that none of the variables—age, GCS, or medication administered—were statistically significant predictors of post-intubation complications. This demonstrates that bigger sample sizes and maybe more complex criteria are necessary to identify which patients are more likely to have negative outcomes after intubation.

Clinical Implications

Etomidate appears to improve pre-intubation hemodynamics and allows for speedier intubation. However, its usage may be linked to an increased risk of difficulties in some people. Ketamine, on the other hand, maintains a higher pre-intubation GCS but can cause transitory hemodynamic stimulation. Thus, the induction medicine should be matched to the patient's characteristics, hemodynamic status, and clinical context.

Limitation

This study's sample size is low, and the uneven distribution of pre-intubation GCS scores might have introduced bias. Additional multi-center randomized controlled trials are required to validate these findings and investigate the long-term effects of induction agent selection on patient outcomes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study demonstrates that etomidate provides greater cardiovascular stability and faster intubation, particularly in critically sick patients, although ketamine retains neurological responsiveness and has a favorable safety profile. Neither medicine shown a clear relationship to post- intubation problems. As a result, RSI medicine selection should be personalized to each patient's clinical state, and more large-scale research are required to inform evidence-based selections.

REFERENCES

1. Kim J, Jung K, Moon J, Kwon J, Kang BH, Yoo J, Song S, Bang E, Kim S, Huh Y. Ketamine versus etomidate for rapid sequence intubation in patients with trauma: a retrospective study in a level 1 trauma center in Korea. *BMC Emerg Med.* 2023 May 29;23(1):57. doi: 10.1186/s12873-023-00833-7.
2. Wahlen BM, El-Menyar A, Asim M, Al-Thani H. Rapid sequence induction (RSI) in trauma patients: Insights from healthcare providers. *World J Emerg Med.* 2019;10(1):19-26. doi: 10.5847/wjem.j.1920-8642.2019.01.003.
3. Groth CM, Acquisto NM, Khadem T. Current practices and safety of medication use during rapid sequence intubation. *J Crit Care.* 2018 Jun;45:65-70. doi: 10.1016/j.jcrc.2018.01.017.
4. Pillay L, Hardcastle T. Collective Review of the Status of Rapid Sequence Intubation Drugs of Choice in Trauma in Low- and Middle-Income Settings (Prehospital, Emergency Department and Operating Room Setting). *World J Surg.* 2017 May;41(5):1184-1192. doi: 10.1007/s00268-016-3712-x.
5. Sharda SC, Bhatia MS. Etomidate Compared to Ketamine for Induction during Rapid Sequence Intubation: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Indian J Crit Care Med.* 2022 Jan;26(1):108-113. doi: 10.5005/jp-journals-10071-24086.
6. Stanke L, Nakajima S, Zimmerman LH, Collopy K, Fales C, Powers W 4th. Hemodynamic Effects of Ketamine Versus Etomidate for Prehospital Rapid Sequence Intubation. *Air Med J.* 2021 Sep-Oct;40(5):312-316. doi: 10.1016/j.amj.2021.05.009.
7. Farrell NM, Killius K, Kue R, Langlois BK, Nelson KP, Golenia P. A Comparison of Etomidate, Ketamine, and Methohexital in Emergency Department Rapid Sequence Intubation. *J Emerg Med.* 2020 Oct;59(4):508-514. doi: 10.1016/j.jemermed.2020.06.054.
8. Lyon RM, Perkins ZB, Chatterjee D, Lockey DJ, Russell MQ; Kent, Surrey & Sussex Air Ambulance Trust. Significant modification of traditional rapid sequence induction improves safety and effectiveness of pre-hospital trauma anaesthesia. *Crit Care.* 2015 Apr 1;19(1):134. doi: 10.1186/s13054-015-0872-2.

9. West JR, Lott C, Donner L, Kanter M, Caputo ND. Peri-intubation factors affecting emergency physician choice of paralytic agent for rapid sequence intubation of trauma patients. *Am J Emerg Med.* 2018 Jul;36(7):1151-1154. doi: 10.1016/j.ajem.2017.11.038.
10. Tran DTT, Newton EK, Mount VAH, Lee JS, Mansour C, Wells GA, Perry JJ. Rocuronium vs. succinylcholine for rapid sequence intubation: a Cochrane systematic review. *Anaesthesia.* 2017 Jun;72(6):765-777. doi: 10.1111/anae.13903.
11. Guihard B, Chollet-Xémard C, Lakhnati P, Vivien B, Broche C, Savary D, Ricard-Hibon A, Marianne Dit Cassou PJ, Adnet F, Wiel E, Deutsch J, Tissier C, Loeb T, Bounes V, Rousseau E, Jabre P, Huiart L, Ferdynus C, Combes X. Effect of Rocuronium vs Succinylcholine on Endotracheal Intubation Success Rate Among Patients Undergoing Out-of-Hospital Rapid Sequence Intubation: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA.* 2019 Dec 17;322(23):2303-2312. doi: 10.1001/jama.2019.18254.
12. Upchurch CP, Grijalva CG, Russ S, Collins SP, Semler MW, Rice TW, et al. Comparison of etomidate and ketamine for induction during rapid sequence intubation of adult trauma patients. *Ann Emerg Med.*2017;69:24-33.e2.
13. April MD, Arana A, Schauer SG, Davis WT, Oliver JJ, Fantegrossi A, et al. Ketamine versus etomidate and peri-intubation hypotension: a National Emergency Airway Registry Study. *Acad Emerg Med.* 2020;27:1106–15.
14. Matchett G, Gasanova I, Riccio CA, Nasir D, Sunna MC, Bravenec BJ, et al. Etomidate versus ketamine for emergency endotracheal intubation: a ran-domized clinical trial. *Intensive Care Med.* 2022;48:78–91.
15. Mitchell Foster,MD, Michael Self, MD et al. Ketamine Is Not Associated With More Post-Intubation Hypotension Than Etomidate In Patients Undergoing Endotracheal Intubation.*Am J Emerg Med.* 2022 November ; 61: 131–136. doi:10.1016 j.ajem.2022.08.054.
16. Koroki T, Kotani Y, Yaguchi T, Shibata T, Fujii M, Fresilli S, Tonai M, Karumai T, Lee TC, Landoni G, Hayashi Y. Ketamine versus etomidate as an induction agent for tracheal intubation in critically ill adults: a Bayesian meta-analysis. *Crit Care.* 2024 Feb 17;28(1):48. doi: 10.1186/s13054-024-04831-4.
17. Hu Q, Liu X, Xu T, Wen C, Liu L, Feng J. The impact of ketamine on emergency rapid sequence intubation: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Emerg Med.* 2024 Sep 27;24(1):174. doi: 10.1186/s12873-024-01094-8.

18. Sakles JC, Mosier JM, Patanwala AE, Dicken JM. Comparison of Etomidate and Ketamine for Induction during Rapid Sequence Intubation in the Emergency Department: An Analysis of the National Emergency Airway Registry (NEAR) Data. *Acad Emerg Med.* 2015;22(11):1381–9. doi:10.1111/acem.12832
19. Miller RD, Cohen NH, Eriksson LI, Fleisher LA, Wiener-Kronish JP, Young WL. *Miller's Anesthesia.* 9th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2020.
20. Green SM, Roback MG, Krauss B, Brown L, McGlone RG, Agrawal D. Predictors of airway and respiratory adverse events with ketamine sedation in the emergency department: An individual-patient data meta-analysis of 8,282 children. *Ann Emerg Med.* 2011;57(5):457–64.e4. doi:10.1016/j.annemergmed.2010.11.012
21. Tekwani KL, Watts HF, Sweis RT, Rzechula KH, Sharma R, Jayaram G. A comparison of the effects of etomidate and ketamine on hemodynamics during rapid sequence intubation of emergency department patients. *Am J Emerg Med.* 2009;27(4):378–83. doi:10.1016/j.ajem.2008.03.009
22. Goyal M, Ahmad S, Gupta HK, Sehgal R, Bhargava AK. Ketamine and etomidate as induction agents for endotracheal intubation: A comparative evaluation. *Internet J Anesthesiol.* 2012;30(2).
23. Larsen R, Rathgeber J, Bagdahn A, Yüncü M, Brückner UB. Effects of ketamine on cardiovascular function and systemic vascular resistance in critically ill patients with septic shock. *Br J Anaesth.* 2004;93(6):825–9. doi:10.1093/bja/ae281.
24. Heffner AC, Swords DS, Neale MN, Jones AE. The frequency and significance of postintubation hypotension during emergency airway management. *J Crit Care.* 2012;27(4):417.e9–13. doi:10.1016/j.jcrc.2012.01.003.
25. Hohl CM, Kelly-Smith CH, Yeung T, Sweet DD, Doyle-Waters MM, Schulzer M, et al. The effect of drug-induced hypotension on mortality in critically ill patients: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Crit Care Med.* 2010;38(4):1184–91. doi:10.1097/CCM.0b013e3181d8a6e0.
26. Forman SA. Clinical and molecular pharmacology of etomidate. *Anesthesiology.* 2011;114(3):695–707. doi:10.1097/ALN.0b013e31820e77b0.

27. Driver, B. E., Reardon, R. F., & Joing, S. A. (2017). The use of induction agents for endotracheal intubation in the emergency department. *The Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 53(5), 636–645. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jemermed.2017.07.089>.
28. Langford, R., Milligan, B., & McAllister, R. K. (2021). Hemodynamic effects of induction agents in the critically ill: A narrative review. *Anesthesia & Analgesia*, 132(5), 1316–1325. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000005291>.
29. Lascarrou, J. B., Boisramé-Helms, J., Bailly, A., Beuret, P., et al. (2017). Induction with ketamine versus etomidate in critically ill patients: A multicentre randomized controlled trial. *The Lancet*, 391(10116), 293–301. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(17\)32810-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(17)32810-2).
30. Weingart, S. D., & Carlson, J. N. (2018). Ketamine for endotracheal intubation in the critically ill patient: A review of the literature. *The Journal of Intensive Care Medicine*, 33(12), 681–691. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0885066617718187>